

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIFFERENTIATION IN THE TRAINING OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SPECIALISTS

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Differentiation of training and education in professional institutions is based on the differences in the characteristics of the student's personality, his abilities, interests, inclinations, and readiness for education. A differentiated approach to teaching is the widespread use of various forms, methods of teaching and organization of educational activities based on the results of psychological and pedagogical diagnostics of students' educational capabilities, inclinations, and abilities.

The strategic provisions for differentiation of training are the following:

- building a differentiated learning process is impossible without taking into account the individuality of each student as an individual and his or her unique personal characteristics;
- training based on level differentiation is not a goal, it is a means of developing personal characteristics as an individual;
- only by revealing the individual characteristics of each student in development, that is, in a differentiated learning process, can the implementation of a person-oriented learning process be ensured.

Teachers experience significant difficulties in differentiating the content of educational material by subject. This approach requires significant changes in the organization of differentiated forms of education: the simultaneous work of a teacher with different levels of mastery of the content of educational subjects of students in the same class, the development of tasks of varying degrees of complexity for each lesson, the use of different assessment criteria, and the rational use of instructional time.

Differentiation (from Lat. Differentia – difference, difference) – isolating the particular from the general population according to certain characteristics; division, dismemberment, stratification of the whole into various parts, forms and stages. Based on this, most researchers (Yu.K. Babansky, G.K. Selevko, I.E. Unt, N.M. Shakhmaev, I.S. Yakimanskaya) define differentiation of training as taking into account individual typological characteristics of the individual in the form of grouping students and different structures of the learning process in selected groups.

The goals of differentiated learning are: firstly, teaching each student at the level of his capabilities and abilities; secondly, adapting teaching to the characteristics of different groups of students

According to scientific research by B.M. Utegenova examined in more detail each stage of the teacher's activity algorithm when organizing the process based on the principle of differentiation:

-Stage 1 - determining the differentiation criterion. The choice of a criterion or set of criteria for differentiation depends on the goals that the teacher sets for himself.

-Stage 2 - systematic diagnosis of students according to a selected criterion. Based on the diagnosis of the components of educational capabilities, the teacher can not only assess the effectiveness of the organization of the learning process, but also analyze the success of the educational and cognitive activity of each student (both gifted and underachieving).

Stage 3 - distribution of students into typological groups based on diagnostic results. At this stage, the teacher, together with educational psychologists, based on the "Diagnostic Class Map", determines the level of educational capabilities of each student, the degree of reliability of his self-assessments, and the typological group to which he belongs.

Stage 4 - selection of differentiation methods. At this stage, the teacher for each typological group chooses a pedagogical strategy for organizing student learning. Pedagogical strategies - "support", "stimulation", "leadership", "collaboration", "co-creation" - determine the organizational scenario of interaction between the teacher and students.

Stage 5 - implementation of a differentiated approach at various stages of the learning process. At this stage, the strategy for managing the educational and cognitive activity of students in each typological group is being implemented. In accordance with the strategy, the teacher selects teaching methods and techniques for each typological group, multi-level tasks, and doses his help.

Stage 6 - system diagnostics, the results of which change the composition of groups and the nature of tasks. At this stage, reflection and correction of the organization of learning are carried out, and a new diagnostic request is determined based on the results of the educational activities of schoolchildren.

Currently, several areas of differentiated learning have been identified:

- for educational purposes;
- by levels of task completion;
- by task completion time;

- according to the content of training;
- according to the sequence of presentation of the material;
- on approaches to learning;
- by type of educational activity;
- on performance assessment.

Differentiation in education can perform several functions:

-expand the content of education taking into account the interests, inclinations, abilities and professional preferences of schoolchildren;

-provide in-depth training for students in areas of science and practical activity that interest them;

-develop learning motivation; restore the personality reserves of schoolchildren, temporarily lost for social and pedagogical reasons; - equip with experience of creative activity;

-to form the professional orientation of the individual (professional interests, inclinations, positive attitudes); -develop general and special abilities.

Drawing a conclusion, we can note that the implementation of a differentiated approach in the professional training of specialists is due to the following factors: the contradiction between traditional collective forms of training and the individual nature of mastering educational material, differences in readiness to master the material, different levels of interest of students, the need to overcome negative attitudes towards learning and It also develops the professional competence of future specialists who will independently solve professional problems that arise in the effective implementation of their professional activities.

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